

CULTiVATE

Food sharing in Brno

Impact report

Jennifer Lyons & Anna Davies

November 2025

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Overview

51 Food sharing initiatives mapped in Brno

38 Initiatives include redistributing food, saving surplus food from disposal and providing food for those in need

17 Initiatives include cooking and eating together, strengthening social connection and improving nutrition

24 Initiatives include growing food, reducing food costs for participants and for supporting physical and mental wellbeing

21 Initiatives undertake more than one activity around food, contributing to a more circular bioeconomy

Annual estimated FSI impacts in Brno from 51 FSIs*

Social	152,991 meals shared	
Economic	52 tonnes of food produced	
Environmental	69,147 tonnes CO ₂ e avoided	
Civic engagement	1,632 volunteers active	

**Impacts estimated using The Toolshed SIA and the CULTIVATE Food Sharing Map.*

Executive Summary

Food Sharing Initiatives (FSIs) support people to grow, cook, eat, and redistribute food together, as well as share knowledge and spaces. They can contribute significantly to more sustainable, resilient, and socially connected urban food systems.

This report presents estimated sustainability impact scenarios for Brno, combining a snapshot of results from the automated mapping of FSIs in Brno using CULTIVATE's Food Sharing Mapping tool with data from sustainability impact assessments (SIA) conducted by FSIs. Scenarios provide low, medium and high estimates of sustainability impact at the city scale.

How to use this report

This report can be used to help support transitions to more sustainable food systems in Brno. This includes using the report:

- **As an evidence base:** Use these scenarios as a baseline from which to track and monitor FSI sustainability impacts over time.
- **For policy evaluation:** Identify where FSI activities currently take place and where there are gaps in provision to ensure municipal and national food, climate and community goals are met.
- **For goal tracking:** Map contributions from FSIs to the global sustainable development goals and to local food and food waste targets.

Food sharing in Brno

Using CULTIVATE's automated Food Sharing Map, FSIs with a digital presence (web, app, social media) were identified and categorised by activity type: Growing; Cooking & Eating; Redistribution; Multifunctional (e.g. engaging in more than one activity). Brno has an emerging food sharing landscape, shown below:

Geolocated FSIs (2025)

In Brno, the geolocated FSIs concentrate most heavily in the central urban core, particularly in and around the historic centre. This clustering aligns with areas where population density and social diversity are highest, and is a typical pattern found in other European cities.

A band of FSIs extends northeast and northwest of the centre, along radial transport corridors, with many undertaking redistribution activities. Several initiatives appear towards the southern periphery, where additional space may support storage, logistics, or small growing sites. By contrast, the southwestern and southeastern districts of Brno-Bohunice and Brno-Slatina display fewer visible FSIs. This suggests the potential influence of land-use zoned for the university or industry, limited digital visibility of local actors, or fewer community-based food initiatives operating with an online or map-identifiable presence.

Mapping of FSIs is the first phase of the SIA calculation process which is set out below.

City-scale impact estimation

Impacts were calculated using a four-step process:

1. **Map** – Identifying FSIs and classifying them according to their activity type.
2. **Calculate** – Estimating a) the mean average impact estimation per indicator category b) the low impact estimation and c) the high impact estimation, using SIA data from all forms of FSIs across nine European cities, as follows:
 - Growing – tonnes of food produced
 - Cooking and eating – number of meals shared
 - Redistribution – Tonnes of CO₂e avoided
 - All FSIs – Number of volunteers engaged
3. **Scale** – Multiplying the number of FSIs in each activity category by the a) mean average b) lowest and c) highest impact figure from CULTIVATE FSI SIA impact data to generate city-level estimates.
4. **Scenarios** – Illustrating the range of possible outcomes in municipal food sharing activity.

Brno impact scenarios

The table below presents the mean, low and high sustainability impact assessment scenarios for Brno.

Food sharing activity	Adjusted No. of FSIs	CULTIVATE average impact per FSI	Mean Impact Scenario Brno	Low Impact Scenario Brno	High Impact Scenario Brno	Metric
Growing	n.13	4	52	18	413	Tonnes food produced
Cooking & Eating	n.11	13,908	152,991	550	987,800	Meals shared
Redistribution	n.27	2,561	69,147	3456	432,000	Tonnes CO ₂ e avoided
All FSIs	n.51	32	1,632	995	5,763	Volunteers

These results provide an early indication of the scale of FSI impacts across Brno from 51 FSIs that have a digital trace.

Expanding reporting practices within existing FSIs would create a broader picture of the sustainability impacts that the FSIs are creating beyond the narrow quantitative categories detailed in the table above. Research shows that FSIs [create impact across a range of social, economic, environmental and governance areas](#) contributing to urban sustainability, food waste reduction, and community resilience. Other FSIs may not have a digital profile or may not have a geolocation profile that the mapping tool can access, so do not currently appear on the map. These can be manually added if indicated and verified.

Recommendations

FSIs in Brno play a vital role in advancing urban sustainability through food for those who can access them. They save and share surplus food, build community, and enhance resilience. Even with preliminary mapping data and limited impact data points from 51 FSIs, their contributions are clear, measurable and meaningful.

Recommendations are to:

1. **Embed data collection** – Use mapping and SIA data to inform policy making. Strengthening data collection will help inform effective, inclusive urban food policy.
2. **Strengthen the FSI ecosystem** – Use data on the distribution of FSIs and compare with the needs of populations to identify areas where FSIs should be supported. Use SIA data to evidence how FSIs can support unmet needs.
3. **Resilience planning** – Integrate FSIs into local food, health, and emergency planning frameworks.
4. **Food waste reduction** - Demonstrate urban-scale contributions to EU food-waste targets from FSIs to track progress toward 30% waste-reduction goals.

If you would like to know more about the method and data underpinning this SIA report, or if you would like to contribute to expanding the food sharing map, contact us at: info@sharingsolutions.eu